

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B159
Date: 19 Jan 2006
Take Off: 09:09:00
Landing: 13:47:05
Flight Time: 4h38m05

Campaign: DABEX
Trials Instructions: North – South sampling of dust and biomass burning plumes
Operating Area: Over land area between Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E), Banizoumbou (13.522°N, 2.629°E) and Djougou to the south (9° 45'36"N, 1°35'56"E).

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Jim Haywood	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CCN	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	CVI / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	Filters	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	SWS / SHIMS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	AMS	Gerard Capes	University of Manchester
13	Mission Scientist 2	Theiry Lebel	IRD AMMA
14	Wet Neph	Martin Glew	Met Office
15	IR Camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
16	Mission Scientist 3	Ayou Moumouni	ASECNA
17	Mission Scientist 4	Jaques Pelon	CNRS
18			

Flight Track:

B159 Track 19-JAN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b159

Date: 19 Jan 2006

Project: DABEX

Location: south of Niamey

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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083144		INU	0.75 kft	123	to NAV
083239		gps	0.74 kft	123	13' 28.66N 2' 10.53E Niamey pan
085954		Heimann	0.00 kft	123	Cal 14
090900		T/O	0.00 kft	270	Niamey
091115		port aft dlu	3.0 kft	182	reset - no pressure - ok
091210		Heimann	4.4 kft	179	shutter open
091321		video	5.0 kft	102	#1 ufc #2ffc
091706	092444	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.77 kft	029	f150>50' 'missed appr oach' to 50'
091949		interrupt P1	2.4 kft	339	
092147		resume P1	2.2 kft	286	2300'
092445	094034	Profile 2	0.75 - 15.0 kft	272	50' climb away
094301	094731	Profile 3	15.0 - 10.0 kft	244	
094731	095556	Run 1	10.0 kft	240	
095205		bbr	10.0 kft	250	retract
095432		heimann	10.0 kft	247	cal 11
095556	095848	Profile 4	10.0 - 8.0 kft	251	
095848	101130	Run 2	8.0 kft	137	
100909		heimann	8.0 kft	079	cal 11
101130	101417	Profile 5	8.0 - 6.0 kft	075	
101418	102754	Run 3	6.0 kft	298	500'/min profile
102431		heimann	6.0 kft	252	cal 11
102754	103718	Profile 6	6.0 - 1.4 kft	255	500'/min profile
103718	104935	Run 4	1.4 kft	072	
103851		video	1.3 kft	068	#3 ufc #4 ffc
104647		heimann	1.4 kft	069	cal 14
104800		!	1.4 kft	070	sat overpass
104935	105313	Run 5	1.5 kft	258	end run 4
105323	105434	Orbit 1	1.4 kft	145	
105712	105816	Orbit 2	2.1 kft	148	1000' agl stbd
105855	105957	Orbit 3	2.1 kft	149	port
110033	110128	Orbit 4	2.0 kft	300	stbd
110323	111412	Profile 7	2.4 - 14.0 kft	192	
110436		bbr	4.0 kft	178	extend
111531	113655	Profile 8	14.0 - 1.5 kft	182	
112747		interrupt P8	3.2 kft	167	
112747	113355	Run 6	3.1 kft	169	started 112747
113355		resume P8	3.1 kft	168	
113538		!	1.9 kft	167	fire photograph
113646		fire	1.5 kft	166	port side
113655	120606	Run 7	1.5 - 2.2 kft	167	
113827		fire	1.4 kft	167	to port
113904		fire	1.4 kft	173	penetrate plume
114005		nev	1.5 kft	168	zero
114023		fire	1.6 kft	168	to port
115401		smoke	1.7 kft	226	
115616		village	1.9 kft	244	to port
120113		fire	2.0 kft	221	to stbd
120255		heimann	1.8 kft	221	cal 14
120443		fires	2.0 kft	220	x2 large 5 miles stbd
120604		video	2.1 kft	220	#5 ufc #6 ffc
120649	120744	Orbit 5	2.6 kft	112	
120831	120930	Orbit 6	2.5 kft	234	
120957	121059	Orbit 7	2.7 - 2.5 kft	243	
121203	121302	Orbit 8	2.5 - 2.6 kft	326	
121403	121601	Profile 9	2.7 - 5.0 kft	045	
121642	123133	Run 8	5.0 kft	040	
122953		heimann	5.0 kft	042	cal 14

123133	123343	Profile 10	5.0 - 7.0 kft	041
123343	123743	Run 9	7.0 kft	042
123743	123822	Profile 11	7.0 - 6.5 kft	042
123822	131944	Run 10	6.5 - 6.4 kft	040
131826		heimann	6.5 kft	344 cal 14
131944	132030	Profile 12	6.4 - 5.8 kft	342
132016		video	5.9 kft	032 #7 dfc #8 ffc
132114		local sample 1	5.8 kft	089 start
132305		!	5.9 kft	088 mark 1
132346		!	5.8 kft	086 mark 2 (late call)
132517		local sample 1	5.8 kft	351 end
132536		local sample 2	5.9 kft	307 start
132720		!	5.9 kft	269 mark 1
132742		!	5.9 kft	275 mark 2
132948		local sample 3	5.8 kft	263 start
133307		!	5.8 kft	090 mark 1
133335		!	5.9 kft	089 mark 2
133405		local sample 3	5.8 kft	113 end
133445	133910	Profile 13	5.9 - 3.8 kft	133
133910		local sample 4		start
		FM pc		crash
134040				mark 1
134103				mark 2
		local sample 5		
				mark 1 (v late call)
134404				mark 2
134705		Land		Niamey
		FM pc		restart
135301		!	0.88 kft	325 stop stand 1
135336		heimann	0.87 kft	325 cal 14
135441		INU	0.88 kft	325 13' 26.28N 2' 10.18E
135631		heimann	0.87 kft	325 cal complete

B159 Track 19-JAN-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: north-south sampling biomass burning plumes

Flight No: B159

Date: 19 January 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling at various altitudes of mineral dust and biomass burning aerosol around and to the south of Niamey.

Location:

Over land area between Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E), Banizoumbou (13.522°N, 2.629°E) and Djougou to the south (9° 45'36''N, 1°35'56''E).

Raster point #137 (13°38'N, 2°45'E)

Raster point #142 (13°23'N, 1°55'E)

Weather:

High loadings of mineral dust and biomass burning aerosols. Cloudless skies preferred. Terra overpass at 10:30, Aqua at 13:30, and Envisat at 10:26.

Special requirements:

Missed approach (50ft) over Niamey airfield and low-level (500ft) flying over land. Local racetrack sampling landing.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Niamey.
2. Ascend to 5000ft and carry out a missed approach descent to 50ft over Niamey airfield [15mins, T=15mins].
3. Broken profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 (or above the aerosol layer), at a rate of 1000ft/min to raster point #137 (13.38°N, 2.45°E) [20mins, T=35mins].
4. A series of four SLRs between raster point #137 and raster point #142 at heights to be decided by the aircraft scientist (e.g. FL100, FL60, FL30, and 500ft) [60mins, T=95mins].
5. Set of four orbits at 600ft (bank angle 50°) over Banizoumbou AERONET site [15mins, T=100mins].
6. (a) A profile ascent to FL150 towards Djougou at 1000ft/min [15mins, T=125mins].
- 6 (b) Profile descent from FL150 to 500ft towards Djougou [15mins]
7. A 'soft ride' terrain following low-level run at 500ft towards Djougou [50mins, T=175mins].
8. Set of four orbits at 600ft (bank angle 50°) over Djougou AERONET site [15mins, T=190mins].
9. Set of SLRs of 15minute duration at three different altitudes (suggest FL50, FL80, FL100) towards raster point #137 [50mins, T=240mins].
10. Profile ascent to FL150 raster point #142 [5mins, T=245mins].
11. Broken profile descent from FL150 between raster point #137 and raster point #142 to FL57 [10mins, 255mins].
12. Local sampling racetrack pattern at FL57, 3700ft, 1700ft [15mins, 270mins].
13. Land at Niamey.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B159

Date: 16th January 2006

Sortie Objectives: DABEX flight #4. The objective was to investigate the in-situ properties of biomass burning and mineral dust aerosols and combinations of the two, together with concurrent radiation measurements.

Operating area: South west Niger, near Niamey and Banizoumbou and between raster points #137 and #142 and also in Benin near Djougou.

Point #137: 13°38'N, 2°45'E.

Point #142: 13°23'N, 01°55'E.

Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E)

Banizoumbou (13.522°N, 2.629°E)

Djougou (9° 45' 36''N, 1°35' 56''E).

Weather: Hazy conditions with significant dust and biomass burning aerosols. Dust concentrations largest in the north of the region and biomass burning aerosols to the south of the region. Possibly a little Ci to the south of the region close to the Djougou AERONET site which may complicate analysis of the orbit data and SHIMS data very close to this site.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take-off, a missed profile descent and ascent (wheels and flaps down) was performed over Niamey airport to FL150. Only a little dust was present in the vertical profile, and it seemed to blend into the BB aerosol at approximately 5000ft. The main BB peak appeared to be between FL60 and FL100. A series of SLRs with profiles inbetween were performed between point #137 and point #142 at FL100, FL80, FL60, and 500ft. The first three of these were in the BB layers and the lowest was made for radiation purposes. Looks to be a very nice study for SHIMS and BBRs. A series of four orbits (LWD, RWD, LWD, RWD) were then performed at 55degrees angle of bank (aircraft too heavy for 60degrees). These were free from Ci. A profile ascent to FL140 and descent to 3000ft were then performed from 2000ft to FL140 in a southerly direction towards Djougou. A soft-ride terrain following run at 500ft AGL was then performed to Djougou. During this long run, many varied habitats were observed – some were extremely free from habitation and some were more inhabited. Burned areas and sporadic fires were observed and encountered during this run. Fields were clearly defined towards the end of the run on approach to Djougou. Surprisingly, almost all of the run was suggestive of mineral dust aerosol, with only very brief interspersions of biomass burning aerosol in the immediate area of fires. A series of 60degree banked orbits were then flown (LWD, RWD, LWD, RWD), but there could be some cirrus contamination. A reciprocal run was then performed at 5000ft within the BB aerosol layer, FL70, which was too close to the top of the aerosol layer so the run was dropped to FL65 back towards Niamey. This means that the outward SLR from Niamey to Djougou can be used for radiation studies with in situ sampling on the way back from Djougou to Niamey. A racetrack descent into Niamey airport was then performed for the IRC at FL57 (three times, but the first two missed the target), then 3,700ft, then 1,700ft. The Heimann was then operated on taxiing the aircraft to the stand.

Summary: Excellent in terms of both in-situ sampling and radiation measurements. The cirrus did not really hamper the flight (except for the extreme south of the operating area). The work close to Banizoumbou/Niamey AMF should be very useful both in lidar validation and in diagnosing the solar radiative effect. The long run to the south to Djougou should be very good for plotting out the direct radiative effect of the aerosols.

Problems:

Wet nephelometer failed (dry neph worked well).

VACC – still U/S.

SWS and SHIMS – only one worked at any one time.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.159**.....

Date 19th Jan 2006.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		→ FL60			Run at FL60, in heavy BB pollution - RBRs flat → good radiation & STIMS run.
10:27:54	End R3 St P6	FL60 ↓			500ft/minute down to Binners burning runs into dust ~ 3000ft. 1000ft @ 10:36:20
10:31:18	End P6 St R4	→ 500ft			Below aerosol → good for STIMS & RBRs.
10:49:35	End R4 St R5	500ft			BBRs ~ 650-700 Wm ⁻² .
⚡					Turn & reposition to Barizomban SLR towards Barizomban.
10:53:23	St O1	700ft			LWD orbit.
10:54:35	End O1				Too low for O2.
10:57:12	St O2	1000 ft			55 degree banked orbit.
10:58:16	End O2				RWD O2 55°
10:58:55	St O3	1000ft			LWD O3 55°
10:59:57	End O3				
11:00:33	St O4	1000ft			RWD O4 60° orbit
11:01:28	End O4				
11:03:23	St P7	2000ft ↑			Start profile
11:14:12	End P7	FL140			End profile above all aerosol
11:15:31	St P8	FL140 ↓			

Good
 No
 Ci.
 Not
 too
 reach
 aerosol

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.159**.....

 Date ...19th Jun... 2006

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:27:47	End St R6	3000ft			Interrupt Profile
11:33:55	St Profile End R6	3000ft ↓			Very hazy, turbulent too. Some fires to RHS.
11:37:17	End R6 St R7	6000ft AGL			Soft terrain following run. 500-600 m PCASP at 11:52
11:52			Neph G ~ B ~ R → mainly dust / large particles		Mix of green vegetation & burned areas. Quite arid. No habitation.
11:55:02					Village RHS, more agriculture
11:57					Fields very visible + villages Visibility improving.
	End R7	1000ft AGL			
	St 05				LWD orbit. 60° orbit set
	End 05				
	St 06				RWD orbit.
	End 06				Djounger directly under us.
	St 07				LWD orbit
	End 07				
	St 08				RWD orbit.
	End 08				Perhaps some Ci contamination in the orbits
	St P9	3000ft ↑			
12:16:42	End P9 St R8	5000ft			Much more typical type BR type of aerosol. Ci at beginning of run, but much better after a few minutes.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B159

Date : 19 Jan 2006

Operator and contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	None
SO₂	None
TDLAS	Not operated
WAS	Not operated

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cals) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
?	Ground	Pre flight
09:14:44	FL050	
09:50	FL100	Bad cal, cut short (started 09:48:58)
09:54:41	FL100	
10:02:23	FL070	
10:17:26	FL060	
10:40:14	500'	
10:59:40	1000'	
11:34:01	FL030	
11:40:11	500'	
12:19:52	FL050	
12:36:38	FL070	
12:39:04	FL065	Quick cal gas check, no full cal required (started 12:38:50)
13:19:07	FL065	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 19/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:17:16	2300	0.11	0	60	30											Start Profile 1 from FL050	
09:18:16	750	0.11	Off	100	70											FL040	
09:19:14	700	0.10	Off	80	25											FL030	
09:24:47	110	0.10	Off	10	8											End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 from 50'	
09:26:50	140	0.10	Off	20	10											FL020	
09:27:58	670	0.10	Off	20	15											FL030	
09:28:55	1200	0.10	Off	50	30											FL040	
09:29:55	1800	0.11	Off	50	Noise											FL050	
09:30:50	1500	0.11	Off	50	Noise											FL060	
09:32:01	1500	0.10	Off	60	Noise											FL070	
09:33:10	1700	0.10		60	Noise											FL080	
09:34:13	1400	0.10		60	Noise											FL090	
09:35:11	1050	0.10		10	Noise											FL100	
09:36:12	270	0.10		5	Noise											FL110	
09:37:12	80	0.09		2	Noise											FL120	
09:38:10	40	0.09			Noise											FL130	
09:39:40	30	0.09			Noise											FL140	
09:40:35	15	0.07			Noise											End of Profile 2 @ FL150	
09:43:04	20	0.08			Noise											Start Profile 3 from FL150	
09:44:17	40	0.08			Noise											FL140	
09:45:09	75	0.09		1	Noise											FL130	
09:46:03	190	0.09		1	Noise											FL120	
09:46:37	380	0.10		1	Noise											FL110	
09:47:28	2050	0.10		10	10											End of Profile 3 & Start Run 1 @ FL100	
09:48:00	1600	0.10		10	10												
09:50:00	1500	0.10		20	20												
09:52:00	1500	0.10		20	10												
09:54:00	1400	0.11		20	10												
09:55:56																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 4 from FL100	
09:57:11	2080	0.11		80	30											FL090	
09:58:44	2000	0.11	1	80	Noise											End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ FL080	
09:59:00	2000	0.11		80	Noise												
10:01:00	1900	0.11		80	Noise												
10:03:00	1800	0.11	1	80	Noise												
10:05:00	1850	0.11	2	80	Noise												
10:07:00	1880	0.11		80	Noise												
10:08:00	1950	0.11		80	Noise												
10:10:00	1900	0.11		70	Noise												
10:11:32																End of Run 2 & Start profile 5 from FL080	
10:12:45	2200	0.11	3	70	Noise											FL070	
10:14:18																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 3 @ FL060	
10:15:00	1900	0.11		70	Noise												
10:17:00	2000	0.11	240	70	Noise												
10:19:00	2000	0.11	Off	70	Noise												
10:21:00	2100	0.11	Off	70	10												
10:23:00	1950	0.11	Off	70	15												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 19/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:25:00	1940	0.10	Off	70	20												
10:27:54																End of Run 3 & Start Profile 6 from FL060	
10:29:51	2100	0.11	Off	70	20											FL050	
10:31:56	1240	0.10	Off	70	15											FL040	
10:34:00	550	0.10	Off	40	15											FL030	
10:37:13																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 4 @ 500'	
10:38:00	550	0.09	Off	40	15												
10:40:00	115	0.12	Off	30	8												
10:42:00	150	0.11	Off	20	10												
10:44:00	140	0.11	Off	20	15												
10:46:00	130	0.12	Off	20	15												
10:48:00	240	0.12	Off	30	15												
10:49:35																End of Run 4 & Start Run 5	
10:53:02																End of Run 5 @ 500'	
10:53:27																Start Orbits	
11:01:28																End of Orbits	
11:03:32	230	0.11	Off	30	Fail											Start profile 7 from 1000'	
11:04:40	410	0.10	Off	20	10											FL040	
11:05:37	1700	0.11	Off	30	10											FL050	
11:06:37	1800	0.11	Off	50	20											FL060	
11:07:22	1780	0.11	Off	60	20											FL070	
11:08:15	1610	0.10	Off	50	20											FL080	
11:09:10	1330	0.10	Off	10	10											FL090	
11:10:07	480	0.08	240	10	Noise											FL100	
11:11:05	260	0.08		5	Noise											FL110	
11:12:10	150	0.09		5	Noise											FL120	
11:13:10	55	0.08		5	Noise											FL130	
11:14:08	30	0.07		2	Noise											End of Profile 7 @ FL140	
11:15:35	35	0.08														Start Profile 8.1 from FL140	
11:16:39	75	0.09		2	Noise											FL130	
11:17:51	120	0.09		2	2											FL120	
11:18:55	550	0.09		2	5											FL110	
11:19:54	1390	0.09		5	5											FL100	
11:21:02	1500	0.09		5	10											FL090	
11:22:05	2500	0.10		10	10											FL080	
11:23:11	2400	0.11														FL070	
11:28:04	800	0.10		70	10											FL030	
11:31:05																Start Run 6 @ FL030	
11:32:00	650	0.09		70	10												
11:33:58																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 8.2	
11:35:11	550	0.10	Off	70	20											FL020	
11:36:53	665	0.09	Off	80	20											End of Profile 8.2 & Start Run 7 @ 500'	
11:37:00	635	0.09	Off	80	20												
11:39:00	900	0.09	Off	80	20											Went through plume	
11:41:00	700	0.09	Off	70	20												
11:43:00	790	0.10	Off	70	20												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 19/01/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:30:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:45:00	530	0.10	Off	60	10												
11:47:00	620	0.10	Off	60	15												
11:49:00	630	0.10	Off	60	20												
11:51:00	650	0.10	Off	60	10												
11:53:00	770	0.09	Off	70	15												
11:55:00	740	0.09	Off	60	10												
11:57:00	760	0.10	Off	60	15												
11:59:00	1000	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:01:00	1200	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:03:00	1400	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:05:00	1600	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:05:55																End of Run 7	
12:06:50																Start Orbits	
12:13:11																End of Orbits	
12:14:14	1300	0.10	Off	50	10											Start Profile 9 form FL025	
12:14:59	1700	0.10	Off	40	10											FL040	
12:16:00	2200	0.10	Off	40	10											End of Profile 9 @ FL050	
12:16:42																Start Run 8 @ FL050	
12:17:00	2200	0.10	Off	40	10												
12:19:00	2200	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:21:00	2360	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:23:00	2300	0.10	Off	50	10												
12:25:00	2400	0.11	Off	60	10												
12:27:00	2400	0.11	Off	60	10												
12:29:00	2400	0.11	Off	70	10												
12:31:00	2460	0.11	Off	50	10												
12:31:33																End of Run 8 & Start Profile 10 from FL050	
12:32:37	2100	0.11	Off	50	20											FL060	
12:33:40																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 9 @ FL070	
12:34:00	2000	0.10	280	20	10												
12:36:00	2200	0.11	Off	50	10												
12:37:43																End of Run 9 & Start Profile 11 from FL070	
12:38:22																End of Profile 11 & Start Run 10 @ FL065	
12:39:00	2090	0.11	Off	50	10												
12:41:00	2200	0.10	Off	40	10												
12:43:00	2300	0.10	Off	30	10												
12:45:00	2300	0.11	Off	30	10												
12:47:00	2500	0.10	Off	20	10												
12:49:00	2400	0.10	Off	20	10												
12:51:00	2370	0.10	Off	20	10												
12:53:00	2340	0.10	281	20	10												
12:55:00	2200	0.11		20	10												
12:57:00	2200	0.11		50	10												
12:59:00	1820	0.11		50	10												
13:01:00	2040	0.11	Off	50	10												
13:03:00	2140	0.11	Off	50	15												

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: 159

Date: 19/01/2006

REPROCESSED BY S OSBORNE 13/3/06

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	✓	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	✓	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	✓	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	✓	Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	✓	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	✓	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Nevz signal ≠ 0 FFSSP shows responses not seen by Nevz.
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:****Date:**

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

<p>Preparation of imagery for Core data product</p> <p>iii) WAVE> auto_image</p> <p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:</p> <p>b) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD</p> <p>d) Enter start time 0 if unknown</p> <p>e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown</p> <p>f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">10</p> <p>iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	✓	PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>b) Directory: PMSDATA:</p> <p>c) File generation: Hit enter</p> <p>d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>	✓	
<p>e) TAS: Y</p> <p>f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX</p> <p>g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> <p>h) Start time: 0 if unknown</p> <p>i) End time: 240000 if unknown</p> <p>j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5</p> <p>k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown</p> <p>l) Coefficient choice: 2</p> <p>m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	✓	Note the particle type
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'</p> <p>Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>	✓	
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p> <p>d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	✓	
<p>12) CHECKS:</p>		
<p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		<i>Some 2DC spikes @ 11:00. Same nevz probs.</i>

Page 1

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
094908	094952	FL100		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				0.34	0.40	0.54	0.79	1.15	S
				871	979	1364	1625	2197	D
			1497	373	375	379	379	409	B
			1393	2290	2301	2317	2338	2350	R
				978.7	978.1	978.4	978.3	978.4	P
095855	095935	FL080		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			1782	0.33	0.40	0.54	0.77	1.16	D
			1760	1.34	1081	1473	2502	3014	B
			1743	398	402	400	408	443	R
			1639	2368	2366	2352	2354	2360	P
			1540	987.0	987.0	987.0	987.1	987.0	
100557	100639	FL080		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			1813	0.34	0.40	0.53	0.81	1.15	D
			1791	981	1229	1509	2662	3140	B
			1745	417	420	420	424	449	R
			1673	2352	2344	2319	2295	2284	P
			1576	987.0	987.1	987.1	987.1	987.0	
101422	101505	FL060		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			1856	0.33	0.39	0.53	0.73	1.13	D
			1835	1063	1331	1507	2016	2920	B
			1789	392	397	405	414	438	R
			1717	2302	2310	2326	2342	2359	P
			1620	986.9	987.0	986.9	986.9	987.0	
102112	102151	FL060		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			1889	0.34	0.39	0.52	0.77	1.13	D
			1868	1195	1761	1775	2504	3456	B
			1823	409	419	427	436	464	R
			1750	2360	2384	2381	2379	2379	P
			1663	986.9	986.8	986.9	985.3	985.1	
103726	103759	500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			1997	0.22	0.38	0.54	0.77	1.11	D
			1424	519	741	922	1753	2428	B
			1905	348	347	342	343	349	R
			1829	2271	2267	2272	2283	2296	P
			1726	985	985.1	985	986.9	985.6	
113720	113601	500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			2189	0.31	0.36	0.50	0.70	1.07	D
			2116	1491	328	638	1404	2101	B
			2019	365	327	269	344	345	R
			2007	2357	2394	2379	2345	2359	P
			1930	984.5	984.3	984.3	984.9	984.4	
115157	115245	500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
			2226	0.29	0.36	0.49	0.72	1.05	D
			2182	928	956	1056	1990	2558	B
			2174	314	312	317	327	331	R
			2102	2357	2329	2358	2367	2387	P
			2004	974.5	984.7	984.6	984.7	984.7	

2nd No peak

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.159**.....

 Date 19/01/2006.....

 Operator's name: M. OLEW.....

 Page 2 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks	
103718	R4	500'	10.3	12%	70%	chiller		off - trap emptied	
104935	R4 cont	500'	10.1	11%	63%	chiller		off	
1102	N10	water	collected in	trap	during	orbits		- chiller was off.	
1115	FL145	above	across	Dry Neph	Zero OK.	Wet neph	Blue - 9e-6	Green - 9e-6	Red - 8e-6
1130	R030	FL030	10.4	13%	60%	↑	+30°C	chiller on to get wet neph humidity cap.	
113655	R7	500'agl	10.4	14%	66%	↑	+30°C		
1145	R7	500'agl	10.4	15%	69%	↑	+35°C	chiller temp needed. Outside air was 23°C.	
1149	R7	500'agl	10.3	19%	74%	chiller alarm		- low coolant. Finger in trap. Chiller off	
1206	R7 cont	500'agl	10.1	75%	70%				
1220	R8	FL050	10.2	49%	69%	chiller off		2 fingers in trap.	
1226	R8	FL050	10.2	49%	70%	↑	+34°C	chiller on, trying to get RH up.	
1227	R8	FL050	10.1	51%	79%	↑	+40°C		
123133	R8 cont	FL050	9.8	40%	85%		+40°C	chiller off for profile.	
123243	R9	FL070	10.5	28%	86%	↑	+38°C	chiller on for run	
1236	R9	FL070	10.4	26%	86%	↓	+35°C	chiller to +25°C	
123822	R10	FL085	10.5	44%	76%	↓	+25°C	chiller to +20°C	
1241	R10	FL065	10.0	39%	72%	↑	+33°C	chiller to +35°C	
1243	R10	FL065	10.0	30%	75%	↑	+39°C	chiller to +40°C	
1249	R10	FL065	10.4	23%	90%	↓	+36°C	chiller to +35°C	
1250	R10	FL065	10.3	23%	88%	↓	+33°C	chiller to +30°C	

Wet Nephelometer Log

Flight No **B154**.....

Date **19/01/2006**.....

Operator's name: **M. GLEW**.....

Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
Dry neph zeroed pre-flight on USB hub 4, destined as com 2								
Coms trouble - so sat ^{28:00} can talk to Dry Neph + Chiller on USB hub but not Wet Neph								
wet neph run with chiller on to test leak.								
0820	1-2 fingers	water in trap	after	52.5	runs	running	pump.	
0802	Presort	10.4	17	78	↑	H2O	communicating	Dry Neph ASRL7: INSTR (Hub 1)
w/D ratios to 0.75. Could not zero Wet Neph. Wet Neph ASRL2: INSTR (Hub 4)								
ISR software could not read parameters. Chiller ASRL9: INSTR (Hub 3)								
0825	When back on aircraft	after security	sweep labview	had frozen.	3 fingers	trap	cleared	everything off.
0845	Not able to talk to Neph	before take off	-	chiller on	small	leakage.		
0918	P1	10.1	44%	—	—	—	Unable to talk to wet neph	Dry Neph hums
0921	P1	2200'	9.9	21%	—	—	going down rapidly	3 fingers in trap.
0929	P2	5400'	10.0	66%	68%	—	chiller off.	Talking to wet neph. trap 1/2 full
0938	P2	FL140	10.2	66%	67%	—	Dry neph just above zero	Wet neph red - Se-6, Green - Se-6,
0947	P1	FL100	10.2	20%	62%	—	In biomass layer.	
0950	P1	FL100	10.1	32%	63%	↑ 30'	chiller on	wet neph RH growing no red growth on.
1004	P2	FL080	10.1	49%	80%	—	chiller off.	
1011	P2	FL080	10.0	50%	80%	—	chiller off.	
1014	P3	FL060	10.3	60%	80%	—	chiller off.	3 1/2 fingers in trap.
1027	P3	FL060	10.2	55%	78%	—	chiller off.	

IIR Camera Log

Page 1 of

Flight No: B359

Campaign: DABEX

Date: 19/1/07

Operator: Jess Kern

Fitted lens: 100mm Active NUC = 754126 - NUC3
 Camera angle: -35°. BPM = 16MAS. BPM FPA Temp = 68.588 K.

Start Time	Stop Time	Height	Lat	Long	Remarks
092508	092702	30'			Missed approach Runway + Niamey houses AGC on
093128	093153	FL70			Across river Niger AGC on
100405	100457	FL80			Niamey town. Some flickering on digital image - tried re-wiring digi cables on PC.
103705		500'			Low level near Niamey
103856		~			Crossed river
10406		~			Turnoff road.
	104935	~			End of run 4
11536	11603	FL100			Good river view
	5700				
132200	132800	5700'			Recon 1.1 AGC off Runway to far to port.
132722	132825	5700'			No view of runway
133237	133349				Runway just in view at top of picture
134037	134114	3700'			- This run - runway just to bottom Get some of runway though
134341	134407	1700'			Some of runway & taxiways @ angle to runway

UPPER SHIMS & SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B159** Date **8-13-19** Operator(s) **S Rogers** log page **1** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

SHIMS

09 01 47			DARK	100	500	OK
09 01 46			SCENE	"	"	T=19
09 08 55	TAKE OFF					
09 17 06	P1 ↓	A050				to 50 ft.
09 19 35		~2300ft	DARK	100	500	
09 19 45			SCENE	"	"	
09 24 45	P2 ↑	50ft				to FL150. (missed approach) T=20
09 40 50			DARK	100	500	
09 41 13			SCENE	"	"	T=17
09 43 01	P3 ↓	FL150				to FL100
09 47 31	R1	FL100				CI above? Little visible T=17
09 57	P4 ↓		DARK	100	500	
09 57 16			SCENE	"	"	
09 58 58	R2	FL080				T=18
10 00						Video tape started - see video for image of PC clock for timing.
10 11 30	P5 ↓	FL080				
10 11 41			DARK	100	500	
10 12 10			SCENE	100	500	T=19
10 14 18	R3	FL060				Thin CI above?
10 29 54	P6 ↓	FL060				500ft min. to 500ft.
10 28 03			DARK	100	500	
10 28 21			SCENE	100	500	T=19
10 37 18	R4	500ft				T=17
		"	DARK	100	500	
10 49	SWS					
10 51 26	R5	500ft	DARK	75	500	
10 54 26			SCENE			6F
10 53 23	O1	500ft		75	500	Crash. Lots of clipping! VERY SCARY!
10 55			6F	30	100	
						Climbing 2 1000ft AGL T=19
10 57 12	O2	1000ft	6F	30	100	
10 58 55	O3		6F	30	150	
11 00 33	O4		6F	30	150	T=20
			DARK	30	150	
11 02			DARK	30	100	
11 02 50			DARK	75	500	
11 03						
11 03 23	P7 ↑					

UPPER SHIMS & SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 159** Date **19 Jan** Operator(s) **S Rogers** log page **2** of **3**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

#	SHIMS					
	P7 ↑					
11 04			DARK	100	500	T=20
11 05 27			SCENE	100	500	
11 15 31	P8 ↓	FL140				to 2000 ft.
	R6					interplay P8
11 32 09			DARK	100	500	
11 32 16			SCENE	100	500	T=19
11 34	P8 ↓					P8 resumed to 500ft
11 36 55	R7	500ft				500ft following termin. T=20
11 51 58		"	DARK	100	500	
11 52 07		"	SCENE	100	500	T=19
06 04			DARK	100	500	
	SWS					
12 01	05		SCENE	30	150	
12 03	06		6F	30	150	
12	07					
12 12 05	08		6F			
12 13			DARK	30	150	
12 13 36			DARK	30	150	
	P9 ↑	500ft?				to FLO50
	SHIMS					
12 14	P9 ↑		DARK	75	500	
12 15 15			SCENE	75	500	
12 16 42	R8	FLO50				T=20
12 31 33	P10 ↑					to FLO70
12 31 36			DARK	75	500	
12 31 -			SCENE	75	500	T=18
12 33 43	R9	FLO70				
12 37 43	P11 ↓					Dropping to FLO65
12 38 22	R10	FL65				
12 43 45		FLO65	DARK	75	500	20
12 43 51			SCENE	75	500	
13 01 01			DARK	75	500	
13 01 09			SCENE	75	500	
13 13 37			DARK	75	500	T=18
13 13 43			SCENE	75	500	
	P12 ↓	FLO65				
	R11	FLO57				Raceback 1st

MICROTOPS II SUNPHOTOMETER

SHEET NO

1

DATE 19 01 2006 SKY CONDITIONS 2
 OPERATOR D. TIDDEMAN FILENAME ONCE DOWNLOADED
 START TIME 0730

Enter Site Details Below:

Site Name in Full	Abbreviate	Latitude	Longitude	Height above sea level(m)
GRAND HOTEL, MIAMI	MIAMI	25	81	50

AOD

TIME	SKY	SITE	MTP Scan Number	AOD (380)	AOD(440)	AOD(675)	AOD(936)	AOD (1020)	WV(g/cm ²)
07:34:53	2/3	MIAMI	59	1.062	0.946	0.667	0.544	0.464	1.73
08:19:24	1	"	60	1.098	0.977	0.683	0.550	0.474	1.80
08:43:38	1	"	61	1.093	0.973	0.683	0.545	0.470	1.84
09:09:15	1	"	62	0.946	0.889	0.625	0.504	0.434	1.73
09:43:00	1	"	63	0.977	0.870	0.606	0.474	0.408	1.73
10:35:05	1	"	64	0.990	0.884	0.624	0.504	0.435	1.74
11:19:47	1	"	65	0.951	0.858	0.611	0.484	0.417	1.69
11:48:43	1	"	66	0.952	0.858	0.616	0.487	0.420	1.71
13:16:19	1	"	67	0.919	0.829	0.598	0.487	0.419	1.69
14:16:00	1	"	68	0.780	0.707	0.522	0.429	0.370	1.56
14:44:53	1	"	69	0.771	0.698	0.515	0.420	0.362	1.54

SKY CONDITIONS: [0] Clear Sky; [1] Haze; [2] Thin cirrus-sun not obscured; [3] Thin cirrus - sun obscured;
 [4] Scattered cumulus - sun not obscured; [5] Cumulus over most of the sky - sun not obscured;
 [6] Cumulus - sun obscured; [7] complete cumulus cover; [8] Status- sub obscured; [9] Drizzle.

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B159

Date:

19 JAN 2005

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run 1	B159Q1	----	----	Top	09:47:30	09:55:56	R1	696	FL100 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 1	B159N1	----	----	Bottom	09:47:30	09:55:56	R1	471	FL100 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 2	B159Q2	----	----	Top	09:58:38	10:11:30	R2	1020	FL080 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 2	B159N2	----	----	Bottom	09:58:38	10:11:30	R2	809	FL080 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 3	B159Q3	----	----	Top	10:14:18	10:27:54	R3	1053	FL060 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 3	B159N3	----	----	Bottom	10:14:18	10:27:54	R3	1006	FL060 in a biomass burning elevated layer, peaking at FL060
Filters run 4	B159Q4	----	----	Top	10:37:18	10:49:35	R4	1284	500 feet within a (possibly) dust layer
Filters run 4	B159N4	----	----	Bottom	10:37:18	10:49:35	R4	1059	500 feet within a (possibly) dust layer
Filters run 5	B159Q5	----	----	Top	11:11:43	11:36:55	R5	2002	Profile ascent and descent towards Djougou, interrupted at 3500 feet; fires observed
Filters run 5	B159N5	----	----	Bottom	11:11:43	11:36:55	R5	1705	Profile ascent and descent towards Djougou, interrupted at 3500 feet; fires observed
Filters run 6	B159Q6	----	----	Top	11:40:03	12:06:06	R6	2509	Run at 500 feet towards Djougou
Filters run 6	B159N6	----	----	Bottom	11:40:03	12:06:06	R6	2176	Run at 500 feet towards Djougou
Filters run 7	B159Q7	----	----	Top	12:16:42	13:00:34	R8	3461	SLR over Djougou at FL050 (until 12:31:33), then climbing at FL070 (12:33:43), adjusted at FL065, then continued at FL060 heading back towards Banizoumbou
Filters run 7	B159N7	----	----	Bottom	12:16:42	13:00:34	R8	2986	SLR over Djougou at FL050 (until 12:31:33),

Filter Sampling Log

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									then climbing at FL070 (12:33:43), adjousted at FL065, then continued at FL060 heading back towards Banizoumbou
Filters run 8	B159Q8	----	----	Top	13:03:07	13:16:00		1216	FL060 towards Banizoumbou
Filters run 8	B159N8	----	----	Bottom	13:03:07	13:16:00		1018	FL060 towards Banizoumbou

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 159

Date: 18th January 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
“ JN02	N	AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	us
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B159

Date: 18th January 2006

Instruments

1. FFC window becoming dirty – bug smears. Ground Eng informed and will clean at next opportunity
2. JW – not zeroing, as on recent flights.

SHIM / SWS – can only operate one or the other
Cloud Physics – FFSSP only good down to FL80 otherwise okay
Core Chemistry – Okay
CVI – okay
Wet Neph – some leak problems
VACC – u/s
Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls DFL calls (2?)

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B159:

Log	Reason
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
4 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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